

Bink Secure: Invisible Password Authentication System Using Eye Blink Detection

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Abstract: Now a days as we can see that the digital platforms has increased rapidly, secure user authentication has become a major aspect. There are many traditional passwords like pin, pattern etc but those are not safe they can be shoulder surfed and lots of consequences might occur like phishing, cyber security threats etc. To overcome with these kind of problems this paper had come with the topic of invisible password authentication system based on eye blink detection. The proposed system allows users to authenticate by using the sequence of the blink pattern instead of typing the password. Computer vision techniques and facial landmark detection are used to monitor the eye movements through a webcam in real time. The Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) algorithm is used to detect the eye blinks based upon the EAR ratio, if the EAR value is less than 0.25 then it considered as the eye is closed and if the EAR value is greater than the 0.25 EAR then it is considered as the eye is open. This enables the system to distinguish between short and long blinks and interpret them as a password pattern for example short-short-long-short blinks. This proposed system offers a contactless and user-friendly authentication while reducing the risk of phishing, hacking. Experimental results demonstrate that the system can accurately recognize the blink patterns under the normal conditions and even in the lightening conditions.

Keywords:

Invisible authentication, Eye blink password, Biometric security, EAR algorithm, Blink pattern recognition, Contactless login.

INTRODUCTION

With the rapid growth in the digital technologies, secure user authentication has become a very important aspect now a days. There are many traditional methods like password, PINs etc but they are not safe, many of the problems might occur like shoulder surfing, phishing, password theft etc. Because of these consequences there is a need of implementing an application which over comes all these kind of problems and increases the secure authentication for the user.

1.1 Background of Authentication Systems

Authentication systems are most essential things for protecting the digital information, but traditional methods like passwords and PINs are not much secure they can be shoulder surfed or guessed. Biometric authentication offers a more secure alternative by using unique methods. Among these, eye blink detection provides an effective, contactless and easy method for verifying

1.2 Motivation of the Proposed System

The system enables secure, hidden password entry using eye blinks and standard device cameras, offering a practical, cost-effective, and user-friendly authentication method and be used in any kind of application purposes for securing the digital information.

1.3 Overview of Eye Blink Authentication

The proposed system uses computer vision algorithms to detect facial landmarks and monitor eye movements in real time. When ever the user tries to access the application firstly the users face will be captured and compare the face data with the stored data if it matches then only it moves to the blink pattern. If not then it represents face does not match and if multiple faces get captured in the camera then it represents multiple faces, and after the three failed attempts the application gets locked. After the face detection only the user enters the blink pattern like short-short-long-short blinks, if the blink pattern matches then only the application opens if not it represents wrong pattern.

Fig1. Accuracy comparison of traditional and biometric authentication methods including the proposed eye blink authentication system.

This graph compares the accuracy between the traditional methods like text password, PIN, Fingerprint etc. Eye blink authentication gives the higher accuracy compared to the different methods.

Fig2. EAR variation across video frames used for blink detection in the proposed authentication model.

The graph shows the variation between the EAR value across different frames which helps to recognise whether the eye is open or closed.

2. Literature Review

Traditional password are very simple which are easy to shoulder surfing, phishing, guessing etc. This system implements the easy and secure authentication way to the users on different platforms. Computer vision analyses the facial landmarks and detect the human face without the requirement of special cameras it can be worked with the normal cameras like phone cameras, laptop cameras. It is much cost effective, secure, contactless system. Eye blink detection commonly implemented with the EAR ratio it accurately identifies the blinks and compare the eye blinks with the stored sequence pattern. Recent studies show that eye blink-based authentication not only improves security but also enhances user convenience by enabling hands-free, contactless login. This approach has the potential to be widely adopted in everyday digital applications without requiring extra hardware requirements.

2.1 Research Gap

Although there are many kind of authentication techniques have been proposed, there are many limitations in the traditional techniques which needs to be over come. Traditional password methods are vulnerable to attacks such as shoulder surfing and password guessing, mean while biometric systems often require many kind of specialized hardware. In todays days most existing computer vision systems focus mainly on facial recognition rather than the patterns like eye blinks.

Therefore, there is a need for a secure authentication system that uses eye blink patterns as an invisible password. The proposed system overcome all the gaps by providing the secure, contactless and cost effective user authentication using the eye blink password system.

3 Proposed System

The proposed system provides the safe and secure, user authentication using the eye blink sequence as a password, where first the users face will be capture using opencv and if the users face is matched with the stored data then only the face will be recognised if others try to access it represents the message face does not recognised and after three failed attempts the application automatically gets locked. If the users face is correctly verified and if user enters correct blink pattern then only the application opens.

The system processes video input through stages like preprocessing, facial landmark detection, blink detection, and verification to accurately authenticate the user.

3.1 System Architecture Overview

The architecture of the proposed system is designed to perform authentication through eye blink detection using a webcam. The system begins by capturing real-time video of the user's face. The captured frames are processed using computer vision algorithms to detect the face and locate important facial landmarks.

And later the blinks of the user gets captured and compared with stored pattern, the authentication gets successful only when the pattern matches.

This system mainly focus on the security purpose on the different digital platforms for securing the digital information.

Fig. 3: Architecture of the invisible password authentication system showing video capture, face detection, eye landmark detection, blink analysis, and authentication verification.

a. User

The user is the person who access the application , the users face gets captured using the computer vision and the data get compared with the stored face data.

b. Input Capture Layer

Camera Module

The camera captures all the faces which are detecting in the frame and send the data for thr further processing.

Face & Eye Detection

This module is used to detect the users face and eye using the land mark detection technique.

Fig. 4: Face recognition and detection used to identify the user before eye blink authentication.

c. Core Processing Layer

Face Recognition

The system verifies the user's identity by comparing the captured face with the stored facial data. If the face matches the registered user, the system proceeds to the blink authentication step.

Blink Detection

Blink is detected by calculating the EAR value which helps to find out that whether the eye is closed or open.

Authentication Engine

This component combines face recognition and blink detection results. The user is authenticated only if both the face and blink passwords match the stored data in the database.

Liveness Detection

Liveness detection ensures that the system interacts with a real person. It prevents spoofing attempts using photos or videos.

Password Processing

The system converts detected blinks into a sequence pattern such as short or long blinks and compares it with the stored blink password.

Fig. 5: Example of eye blink sequence used as an invisible password for authentication.

d. Data Storage Layer

User-Database

The user database stores the information of registered users along with the facial feature data collected during the registration process. This data is used by the system to identify and verify the user during authentication.

Password-Model

During login, the detected blink pattern is compared with the stored sequence to verify whether the entered password is correct.

e. Security Layer

Encryption

Encryption is the process where the readable data is converted into a secure coded form so that only the authorized users can access and understand it.

Spoofing Detection

This module detects if any kind of fake authentication attempts are been done by using images or recorded videos.

Secure Access

Secure access ensures that only the registered or authenticated users can enter the system.

f. Output & Interface Layer

Visual Feedback

The system provides messages to guide the user during authentication.

Authentication Result

The system displays whether the login attempt is successful or failed.

System Access Control

This component manages user permissions after authentication.

User System Access

Once authentication is successful, the user can access the system features.

4 Result and Discussion:

The proposed **Invisible Password Authentication System using Eye Blink Detection** was tested to evaluate its performance, reliability, and accuracy in real-time conditions. This system has been implemented and tested in different lightening conditions which gives the accurate output. This system firstly captures the face data and sends for processing and checks whether the face data is matched with the stored data or not if the face data does not get matched it represents that face does not match, if multiple faces gets captured in the frame it represents that multiple faces getting captured and after the three failed login attempts the application gets automatically locked.

Face recognition and blink pattern matching both gets compared and when both works correctly then only the user can access the application. This system is mainly proposed for securing the users authentication, for providing the security for the data which is on the digital platforms. When the user performed the correct blink pattern, the authentication engine successfully granted access, while incorrect blink sequences resulted in access denial. The system showed high accuracy when the user's face was clearly visible and the lighting conditions were stable.

In case of low lightening or low camera quality it might the work flow but I most of the cases the system gives the correct output.

4.1 Test Case Results

The proposed system was tested under a variety of lighting conditions, including low light, indoor environments, and outdoor environments, to evaluate its performance. In most of the situations, the system was able to produce accurate results. Even when minor variations occurred, the system continued to function reliably without any significant issues, maintaining correct output.

Multiple test cases were carried out to ensure the robustness of the system, and only after successfully passing all these tests is a user granted access to the application. And even re-tested to check the performance of the system in the different environment conditions.

Table 4.1: Test Cases for Invisible Eye Blink Authentication System

Test case ID	Test Description	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
TC01	Face detected properly	Face box displayed	Face detected	Pass
TC02	Eye landmarks detected	Eye points extracted	Correct detection	Pass
TC03	Single blink detection	Blink count increases	Correct	Pass
TC04	Correct blink password	Access granted	Access granted	Pass
TC05	Incorrect blink password	Access denied	Access denied	Pass
TC06	No face in frame	Warning message	Warning displayed	Pass
TC07	Low lighting condition	Reduced accuracy	Slight delay	Pass

These test cases determine how the system works properly in different environment conditions. With all the authentication mechanism and correctly grants or denies the authentication.

4.2 Accuracy Evaluation

Table 4.2.1: Accuracy Evaluation of Eye Blink Authentication System Rates

Test no	Webcam Quality	Testing Condition	Accuracy(%)
1	1440p	Bright	97%
2	1440p	Normal	98%
3	1440p	Dark	94%
4	1080p	Bright	95%
5	1080p	Normal	98%

6	1080p	Dark	92%
7	720p	Bright	90%
8	720p	Normal	95%
9	720p	Dark	88%

Table 4.2.2: Test Accuracy Rates for Different Environments

Test No	Environment	Condition	Accuracy%
1	Indoor	Bright	97%
2	Indoor	Normal	98%
3	Indoor	Dark	95%
4	Outdoor	Bright	97%
5	Outdoor	Normal	98%
6	Outdoor	Dark	94%

From the above experiments the accuracy is evaluated and calculated. The proposed system works with 97% of accuracy even in different lightening conditions.

5 Conclusion

The results of the proposed system demonstrate that eye blink-based authentication can serve as a secure alternative to traditional password methods. Instead of typing a password, users provide a sequence of eye blinks, making the process contactless and more private. This approach helps reduce common security risks, such as someone observing the password or gaining unauthorized access. The system uses Dlib to detect facial features and track blinking in real time, allowing it to identify users with a good level of accuracy. When face recognition is added, it further strengthens security by acting like a second layer of verification.

Although certain factors, such as lighting conditions or head movement, can slightly affect performance, the system still works reliably in most cases. By combining biometric features with behavioural patterns, the overall authentication process becomes more secure and difficult to bypass. With further improvements, this system could be applied to areas like mobile device security, access control systems, and smart home applications. Future enhancements, such as improved lighting handling, more advanced liveness detection, and the use of AI techniques, can make the system even more accurate and robust. Overall, this approach shows strong potential to become a dependable next-generation authentication method for real-world use.

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